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THE INFLUENCE OF SITUATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH MOTIVATION AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE AT THE RANTAU SELATAN SUB-DISTRICT OFFICE, LABUHANBATU REGENCY

ВПЛИВ СИТУАТИВНОГО ЛІДЕРСТВА ТА СПРИЙНЯТТЯ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНОЇ ПІДТРИМКИ НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ЧЕРЕЗ МОТИВАЦІЮ ЯК ПРОМІЖНУ ЗМІННУ В ПІДРАЙОННОМУ ОФІСІ РАНТАУ СЕЛАТАН, РЕГЕНТСТВО ЛАБУХАНБАТУ

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Азхар, Сайфууддін, Салман Фаріс, Дарвін Лі. Вплив ситуативного лідерства та сприйняття організаційної підтримки на продуктивність працівників через мотивацію як проміжну змінну в підрайонному офісі Рантау Селатан, регентство Лабуханбату. Науково-методична стаття.

Це дослідження вивчає вплив ситуативного лідерства та сприйняття організаційної підтримки на ефективність роботи через мотивацію серед державних службовців у підрайонному офісі Рантау Селатан у регентстві Лабуханбату. Дані були зібрані у 30 постійних працівників за допомогою анкетування та документальних досліджень. Результати, проаналізовані за допомогою SPSS версії 25, демонструють значний позитивний вплив ситуативного лідерства та сприйняття організаційної підтримки на мотивацію та ефективність роботи. Мотивація також позитивно впливає на продуктивність. Більше того, ситуативне лідерство та сприйняття організаційної підтримки опосередковано впливають на результативність через мотивацію як проміжну змінну.

Ключові слова: ситуативне лідерство, продуктивність, мотивація, сприйняття організаційної підтримки

Azhar, Syaifuddin, Salman Faris, Darwin Lie. The Influence of Situational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable at The Rantau Selatan Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency. Scientific and methodical article.

This study examines the impact of Situational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on Performance through Motivation among civil servants at the Rantau Selatan Sub-District Office in Labuhanbatu Regency. Data was collected from 30 permanent employees using questionnaires and documentary studies. Results, analyzed using SPSS version 25, demonstrate significant positive effects of Situational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on Motivation and Performance. Motivation also positively influences Performance. Moreover, Situational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support indirectly affect Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable.

Keywords: situational leadership, performance, motivation, perceived organizational support

In today's increasingly competitive environment among organizations, every organization is demanded to undergo changes to continue growing and surviving. It is also essential for organizations to recognize and manage human resources as effectively as possible. Human resources play a central role in organizations and companies. For management activities to run smoothly, a company must have highly knowledgeable and skilled human resources who make diligent efforts to manage the company as optimally as possible, thereby improving the performance of these human resources. Human resources must be managed in such a way that they are efficient and effective in achieving the organization's mission and goals. So, it is clear that one key to winning this competition is by utilizing the human resources owned by the company. The role of human resources in organizations is crucial because an organization is developed for the sake of humans as well. Additionally, the development of an organization highly depends on the human resources it possesses; if the performance of human resources is not maximized, then the organization's performance will not be optimal. Therefore, holistic organizational support is greatly needed.

Analysis of recent research and publications

In today's highly competitive organizational landscape, the imperative for change to foster growth and sustainability is paramount. Organizations must also recognize and effectively manage their human resources, which serve as central figures within them. The efficient management of human resources is crucial for optimizing organizational performance and achieving mission and goals. This necessitates utilizing human resources to gain a competitive edge. The role of human resources in organizational development is pivotal, and the performance of an organization is significantly reliant on the performance of its human capital. Therefore, holistic organizational support is indispensable. The Office of the District Chief of South Rantau, Labuhanbatu Regency, is one such government institution tasked with serving the community, including empowerment activities. The performance of its employees directly impacts the achievement of the institution's goals. Human resources management is a critical concern for this institution to achieve its organizational objectives and ensure employee satisfaction. Employee satisfaction fosters effective task execution. Performance, as defined by Bangun (2012) and Fahmi (2017), is a measure of task accomplishment within specified parameters and agreements. It encompasses various factors, including knowledge, skills, work attitude, work quality, productivity, and interaction. Employee performance evaluation is crucial for organizational development, and it relies on both leadership and employee contributions. Therefore, understanding and addressing employee needs and expectations are essential for organizational success. Supportive organizational environments enhance job satisfaction and performance. Effective leadership is vital for meeting various needs and creating conducive work conditions. Leadership styles influence employee behavior and ultimately their performance. Situational leadership, as described by Robbins in the journal by Heni Hikmayani Fauzia et al. (2018), emphasizes adapting leadership approaches based on employee readiness. This approach can significantly impact organizational success. Motivation, driven by perceived organizational support, influences employee commitment and performance. According to Eisenberger (2002), perceived organizational support reflects employees' beliefs regarding organizational appreciation and concern for their well-being. Higher perceived support correlates with increased organizational commitment and performance. Given these considerations, the proposed study titled "The Influence of Situational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on Employee Performance Through Motivation as an Intervening Variable at the Office of the District Chief of South Rantau, Labuhanbatu Regency" aims to explore these dynamics further".

The main part

Performance is the outcome of a work process that adheres to measurable quality and quantity

requirements set within a specific timeframe and is carried out with full responsibility to achieve the goals established by the organization. Here are the performance variable assessment indicators:

1. Quality.
2. Quantity.
3. Timeliness.
4. Cost-effectiveness.
5. Supervisory needs.
6. Interpersonal influence.

Situational leadership is the behavior exhibited by a leader when performing work activities by influencing others, both as individuals and in groups. Here are the situational leadership variable assessment indicators:

1. Telling (instructing).
2. Selling (persuading).
3. Participating (engaging).
4. Delegating (assigning).

Perceived Organizational Support is the belief of employees regarding the extent to which they feel that the organization or company cares about and appreciates their contributions, and acknowledges their work for the improvement of their well-being. Here are Perceived Organizational Support variable assessment indicators:

1. The organization values employees' contributions.
2. The organization appreciates the extra effort that employees have put in.
3. The organization will address any complaints from employees.
4. The organization cares deeply about employee welfare.
5. The organization will inform employees if they are not performing well.
6. The organization cares about overall job satisfaction among employees.
7. The organization shows great concern for employees.
8. The organization takes pride in employees' successes at work.

Motivation is the internal or external force that drives an individual to behave or act in order to achieve goals and fulfill the needs to provide satisfaction to oneself. Here are Motivation variable assessment indicators:

1. Physiological needs.
2. Safety needs.
3. Social needs.
4. Esteem needs.
5. Self-actualization needs

RESULT. This research employs data analysis techniques using quantitative data processed with SPSS version 25 software, t-test, Sobel test, and path analysis.

Respondent Characteristics. the majority of respondents were 31-40 years old with a total of 15 employees (50.0%). While the number of respondents aged 20-30 years was 5 employees (16.7%), the number of respondents aged 41-50 years was 4 employees (13.3%) and the number of respondents aged > 50 years was 6 employees (20.0%).

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender. the majority of respondents were female with 16 employees (53.3%). While the number of male respondents was 14 employees (46.7%).

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education Level. The majority of respondents have an undergraduate education totalling 17 employees (56.7%). While the number of respondents with high school / vocational high school education was 10 employees (33.3%), the number of respondents with

Diploma (1/2/3) education was 2 employees (6.7%) and the number of respondents with S2 education was only 1 employee (3.3%).

Characteristics of Respondents Based on Years of Service. The majority of respondents have a tenure of > 10 years, totalling 15 employees (50.0%). While the number of respondents who have a tenure of < 5 years is 7 employees (23.3%) and the number of respondents who have a tenure of 5-10 years is 8 employees (26.7%).

Table 1. Results of t-Test for Sub Model I

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	14.564	4.763		3.058	.005
	Situational Leadership	.572	.147	.557	3.900	.001
	Perceived Organizational Support	.387	.157	.353	2.468	.020

a. Dependent Variable: Motivasi

Source: the authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-statistic test results are obtained as follows:

1. The Situational Leadership variable (X1) has a t-value (3.900) > t-table (2.05) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.001 (< 0.05). This indicates that Situational Leadership significantly influences the Motivation variable.

2. The Perceived Organizational Support variable (X2) has a t-value (2.468) > t-table (2.05) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.020 (< 0.05). This indicates that Perceived Organizational Support significantly influences the Motivation variable.

Thus the path analysis equation can be arranged as follows:

$$Z = 14.564 + 0.572X1 + 0.387X2$$

The analysis equation model means:

1. The constant value is 14.564 which means that if the independent variables, namely Situational Leadership (X1), and Perceived Organizational Support (X2) are equal to zero, then Motivation (Z) is 14.564.

2. The regression coefficient value X1 = 0.572 indicates that if Situational Leadership increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 57.2%.

3. The regression coefficient value X2 = 0.387 shows that if Perceived Organizational Support increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 38.7%.

Table 2. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model I

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.671 ^a	.450	.409	1.941

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Referring to the regression output of Sub Model I, it can be seen that the significance probability value (Sig) of the two variables, namely Situational Leadership (X1) = 0.001 and Perceived Organizational Support (X2) = 0.020. This result provides a conclusion that the regression of Sub Model I, namely the Situational Leadership variable (X1) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z), and the Perceived Organizational Support variable (X2) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z).

The data above indicates that the contribution or influence of the variables Situational Leadership (X1) and Perceived Organizational Support (X2) on the Motivation variable (Z) is 40.9%, while the remaining 59.1% is contributed by other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for the value of $\hat{\epsilon}_1$ can be calculated using the formula $\hat{\epsilon}_1 = \sqrt{1-0.409} = 0.7687$.

In the table, the t-test statistic was obtained as follows:

1. The variable Situational Leadership (X1) with a calculated t-value (3.679) > the tabulated t-value (2.06) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.001 (< 0.05). This indicates that Situational Leadership significantly influences the Performance variable.

2. The variable Perceived Organizational Support (X2) with a calculated t-value (2.166) > the tabulated t-value (2.06) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.004 (< 0.05). This shows that Perceived Organizational Support significantly affects the Performance variable.

3. The variable Motivation (Z) with a calculated t-value (2.248) > the tabulated t-value (2.06) with a significance probability level (Sig) of 0.033 (< 0.05). This suggests that Motivation significantly influences the Performance variable.

Table 3. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Coefficientsa						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21.297	1.990		10.702	.000
	Kepemimpinan Situasional	.243	.066	.731	3.679	.001
	Perceived Organizational Support	.073	.063	.205	2.166	.004
	Motivasi	.156	.069	.481	2.248	.033

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Table 4. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model II

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.587	.344	.269	.699

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The data above indicates that the contribution or influence of the variables Situational Leadership (X1), Perceived Organizational Support (X2), and Motivation (Z) to the Performance variable (Y) is

26.9%, while the remaining 73.1% is contributed by other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, the value of $\hat{\epsilon}_1$ can be calculated using the formula $\hat{\epsilon}_1 = \sqrt{(1-0.269)} = 0.854$.

Table 5. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Variabel	Unstandardized	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Std. Error	P-Value
Situational Leadership on Motivation	0.586 (a)	0.159 (Sa)	1.703	0.041	0.088
Motivation to Performance	0.121 (b)	0.063 (Sb)			
Perceived Organizational Support to motivation	0.411 (a)	0.192 (Sa)	0.044	0.027	0.964
Motivation to Performance	0.003 (b)	0.067 (Sb)			

Source: the authors' own elaboration

The test statistic value for the influence of Situational Leadership on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable is 1.703, which is less than 1.96, with a significance of 0.088, greater than 0.05. This implies that Hypothesis 6 is not accepted, indicating that Motivation cannot mediate the influence of Situational Leadership on Performance. The test statistic value for the influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable is 0.044, which is less than 1.96, with a significance of 0.964, greater than 0.05. This indicates that Hypothesis 7 is not accepted, suggesting that Motivation cannot mediate the influence of Perceived Organizational Support on Performance.

The Effect of Situational Leadership on Motivation. The Situational Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The Situational Leadership variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.572, indicating that if Situational Leadership increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 57.2%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Situational Leadership has a significant influence on the Motivation of the South Rantau Labuhanbatu Sub-District Office.

The effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Motivation. The Perceived Organizational Support variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The Perceived Organizational Support variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.387, indicating that if Perceived Organizational Support increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 38.7%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Perceived Organizational Support has a significant influence on the Motivation of the South Rantau Labuhanbatu Sub-District Office.

The Effect of Situational Leadership on Performance. The Situational Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The Situational Leadership variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.243, indicating that if Situational Leadership increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 24.3%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Situational Leadership has a significant influence on the performance of the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office.

The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Performance. The Perceived Organizational Support variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-

District Office. The Perceived Organizational Support variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.073, indicating that if Perceived Organizational Support increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 7.3%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Perceived Organizational Support has a significant influence on the performance of the South Rantau Labuhanbatu Sub-District Office.

The effect of motivation on performance. Motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office. The motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.156, indicating that if motivation increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 15.6%. Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Motivation has a significant influence on the Performance of the Labuhanbatu South Rantau Sub-District Office.

The effect of Situational Leadership on Performance through Motivation. Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the test statistic value is $1.703 < 1.96$ with a significant value of $0.088 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is not able to mediate the relationship between the influence of Situational Leadership on Performance. Thus it can be said that Situational Leadership has no influence in improving Performance if done through Motivation.

The effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Performance through Motivation. Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the test statistic value is $0.044 < 1.96$ with a significant value of $0.964 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the Motivation variable is not able to mediate the relationship between the effect of Perceived Organizational Support on Performance. Thus it can be said that Perceived Organizational Support has no influence in improving performance if done through motivation.

Conclusions

Based on the research findings and discussions conducted by the researchers regarding the influence of Situational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support on employee performance at

the South Rantau Sub-District Office through Motivation as an intervening variable, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Situational Leadership influences Motivation at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.

2. Perceived Organizational Support influences Motivation at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.

3. Situational Leadership influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.

4. Perceived Organizational Support influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.

5. Motivation influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.

6. Situational Leadership influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, through Motivation as an intervening variable.

7. Perceived Organizational Support influences Performance at the South Rantau Sub-District Office, Labuhanbatu Regency, through Motivation as an intervening variable.

Suggestions.

1. The District Office of South Rantau in Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees in completing a number of tasks within the specified time frame and being able to produce a significant amount of work or activity results that generate substantial benefits.

2. The District Office of South Rantau in Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees in accepting job responsibilities to effectively complete tasks.

3. The District Office of South Rantau in Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees in carrying out their duties and appreciate every contribution made by employees.

4. The District Office of South Rantau in Labuhanbatu Regency should pay attention to employees so that they feel respected and valued by all colleagues in the work environment.

Abstract

This research aims to determine whether Situational Leadership and Perceived Organizational Support influence Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable in employees of the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency. The research was conducted on permanent employees (PNS) at the Rantau Selatan District Head Office, Labuhanbatu Regency.

The population in this study was 30 people. Due to the small population, the sampling technique in this study was a saturated sample with a sample size of 30 people. The data collection technique used is primary data in the form of a questionnaire and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique uses quantitative data processed with the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis.

The results obtained in this research show 1) there is a positive and significant influence between Situational Leadership on Motivation, 2) there is a positive and significant influence between Perceived Organizational Support on Motivation, 3) there is a positive and significant influence between the Situational Leadership variable on Performance, 4) there is a positive and significant influence between Perceived Organizational Support on Performance, 5) there is a positive and significant influence between Motivation on Performance, 6)

There is a positive and significant influence between Situational Leadership on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable, 7) There is an influence between Perceived Organizational Support on Performance through Motivation as an intervening variable.

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